

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND ROLE OF ADMINISTRATION IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

Education as an investment constitutes the largest enterprise. It is the principal instrument for academic progress, social mobilization, political survival and effective national development of any country. Investment in education is a necessary condition for promotion of economic growth and national development. Quality higher education system will produce quality skills and quality human capacity. Human Resource Development towards National Development. Thus, this article reviewed the literatures on quality administration and management in higher education with the aims of highlighting the implication of human resource development. This study aims at discussing the management of human resources (HR) at Muhammadiyah University, Jakarta, comprises HR planning, recruitment, selection, training and development, compensation, and performance evaluation activities. This study uses a qualitative method with a case study approach. Data collected from document studies, interviews and observation. Human resources are the key to rapid socio-economic development and efficient service delivery. That's why this paper stressed that without an adequate, skilled and well-motivated workforce operating within a sound human resource management programme, development is not possible. Every educational system at every level depends heavily on the human resources for execution of its programme. The function of human resource management in education includes staff maintenance, staff relations, staff development, procurement of staff and job performance reward. The challenges of human resource management include poor working condition, problem of staffing, funding, incessant transfer of teacher among others. To work in an organization, if ignore from topics theory divisions between management theoretician you need proper programming, organization, leadership, proper human relations, decisions making and goal financial system and precise personnel system. These are very essential and malpractice of any of the above may bring up difficulties in the process of the activities in that organization.

INTRODUCTION

Historic, systemic differences in relation to human resource management continue to exercise significant, although arguably changing, influence. A simplified dichotomy remains between institutions that have power and responsibility as employers of staff, and institutions where this authority rests with the government. In the former instance, the institution can appoint, grade and, at least to a degree, determine the reward of staff, aspects of their conditions of employment, their development, and the building of capacity. Higher education, as the center of excellence, should be able to produce high quality manpower to face the challenges in increased competition in this globalization era. In various literatures, institutions of higher education must carry out three functions; developing human resources, developing

knowledge and technology, and producing agents of change. Those three functions must be fully understood by the administrators and faculty members of a university. Human resources (HR) are the key in the success of a higher education institution to produce graduates who can positively contribute to society. The administration of a school institution has the responsibility for bringing together various resources and allocating them effectively to accomplish the general goals of the institution other nations of the world has an obligation to prepare her citizens for life in a world that is characterized by rapid social, economic, political and technological changes. The relevant levels of government have been investing a substantive resource in setting up educational institutions for this purpose Today's higher education institutions need quality human resources. Therefore, it is necessary to have a training and development program carried out by higher education institutions, where training and development factors are considered the most important to improve employee work performance, as well as increase daily tasks in serving the public. Professional human resource training can be seen as strategic investment to be competitive in the world of work and organizations. Human Resource Management (HRM) is an important instrument for an organization to achieve its various objectives. Human resource management is considered to play an important role in achieving organizational performance, both in higher education institutions and in the public administration sector. Quality human resources have an important role in achieving the targets set, so the bureaucratic managerial process is always in the form of direction, implementation, and evaluation and must be supported by qualified administrative staff. Human resource management concerns the procurement or recruitment, staffing, welfare, maintenance, training and retraining, placement, promotion, motivation relationship, compensation or rewards, transfer and discipline of staff. Human resource management is a basic function of management that determines the performance of staff in any organization. This simple implies that when staff in the education systems are adequately recruited, selected and supervised, inducted and adequately rewarded, and provided for, properly developed, appraised and promoted on the job, they will be committed to the job, remain dedicated and productive in the education systems. Higher education management and Human Resource Development are seriously interdependent; higher education produces human resource for national manpower need and at the same time human resource are inputs for higher education. In this light, higher education in a country is a machinery for development and the human resource input of it must be taken into due consideration, in the management of it, as well as in national character of a country as a whole. Based on the two sideways benefits of Human Resource Development to higher education in a country, the management and administration of higher education must be positioned and effective towards proper input and output of human resource for national growth.

The role of instruction in developing human source :

The development of human sources is the regular instruction that implement in a determined period. Its goal is increasing the human development in doing his or her job we explain the process of human source development in this chapter.

Assessment of operation must have a close relationship with human source instruction. In developing the human source, we must have an assessment of action. It is similar to a doctor that has an exact medical examination of his patient to know his or her illness. In this stage we must determine the shortages and weak points and improve them. The organization will be run by the trained persons if we have the prevention process and improving process simultaneously (Mohammad Rouhi Eaisalou and others, 2011).

The relationship between instruction and management developing needs :

Because of the importance of management instruction and it's developing for imploring the organizations' goal, it is necessary to learn 6 main sources of managing: job knowledge- general information – special personal needs organizational knowledge – commutation skills determination skills (Ibid, 2011).

Management and Administration as Important Factors for HRD in Education

The word management generally implies the art and process of getting things done by others towards the achievement of preset goals and objectives (Keller, Parameswaran, & Jacob, 2011; Richard, 2011). Management involves the implementation of business objectives with a strategic aim of reaping in the gains of business, therefore on this note, the word 'management' as it is applicable in university and higher education management is 'business in nature'. That is when the term management is used and applied in a setting like university and institutions of higher learning; there must be expectation of 'profit and gains' as a result of the fact that management happens in business for the sole aim of profit advancement and survival. In the light of this, when management is conceptualized, in higher education setting, as a tool for output and performance effectiveness; then there is a reference 'profits' accruable from such management expeditions, that is profits in terms of 'high turnout of high-level manpower', 'high return rates to the general economy in terms of technology and production' (Gupta, 2010). Every business operate mainly for survival and profitability, therefore a university as a center of business of human development has to be well managed for the purpose of achieving its goals of survival and profitability in terms of creation and development of relevant skills for the society. In theory, practice and principle a university or an institution of higher learning are not meant to operate for business profit or gain, as a result of the fact that institutions of higher learning are 'not for profit' organizations. Management in this light, is not about material management to increase monetary gains and profits, but the management of available resources towards sustainable human capital and human capacity development for the socio-economic benefit of the country (Ekundayo & Ajayi, 2009). Administration involves formulation of policies and directing activities towards achievement of reset goals and objectives. However, from whichever way one look at the process of controlling process towards efficiency in the university, either from the way of administration or from the way of management, administration should be used to ensure quality for the purpose of adequate and efficient manpower output, in terms of human resource development for the country (Gbenga M. Akinyemi & Other, 2013).

Goals and Role of Human Resource Management in Education

The goals of human resource management in education are to develop the workers and to contribute to goal achievement. Human resource management has some specific roles to play. These are strategic and operational roles.

Strategic Role - Human resources were once relegated to second-class status, but its importance has grown dramatically in the last two decade. Again, its new importance stem from adequately recruited,

selected and supervised, inducted and adequately rewarded, provided for, properly develop, appraised and promoted on the job. They will be committed to the job, remain dedicated and productive in the education system.

Operational Role - Human resources management is therefore, interested in compliance with equal employment opportunities and observation of labour laws; examples; applicants must be oriented to the organizations, supervisors must be trained, safety problems must be resolved; wages and salaries must be administered. A wide range of activities typically associated with the day-to-day management of people as provided by laws and regulations must be performed efficiently.

Functions of Human Resources Management in Education and role of Administration

Human resource management in education is a set of practices and methods of integrating and maintaining the teaching staff in the school so that the school can achieve their purpose and as well as meet the goals for which they were established. It is the motivation and co-ordination of the activities and effort of the teachers in school in order to obtain maximum output from them and consequently achieve the goals of education optimally.

Staff Maintenance - This concern making the work environment conducive for workers, pertinent practices include; promotion and transfer, motivation, staff safety, security and health services. It is pertinent that educational establishments have sound policies in respect of staff transfer and promotion to ensure that justice and fairness prevail in dealing with staff. As work to be performed in the school is important, the mood of the man to perform the job is equally important.

Staff Relations - There must be a good communication network in the school to enable workers to be constantly informed of the progress being made in the school. Workers should be encouraged to participate in planning and decision making in the school. Workers should be encourage by recognizing the staff as human beings with feelings, interest, needs and emotions and treating them as such with fairness and respect.

Staff Development - This is the process of appraising staff performances and identifying their key skills and competence that need development or training to improve their skills for better performance. It involves providing development programme and training courses that are suitable for the programme. The success of educational organization hinges on the strength and quality of the staff members.

Procurement of Staff - Staffing of schools is a job performed by the ministry of education through its agencies in the federal and state government. Procurement of staff in education deals with obtaining people with appropriate and necessary skills, abilities, knowledge and experience to fill the vacant teaching posts in schools.

Job Performance Rewards - This involves the design and administration of rewards for jobs performed.

It is very important that management, ministry of education and its agencies take the issue of reward system very seriously.

Challenges of Human Resource Management in Education - Human resource management has become notably complex in the sense that as human beings, they are not reliable for doing one thing over and over in exactly the same way. They can be expensive depending on their cadres, qualification and skills.

Poor working Condition: A good remuneration tends to reduce inequalities between staff earnings, raise their individual morale, motivate them to work for pay increase and promotions, reduces inter group friction and employee grievances. Teachers' salaries are not paid alongside with other civil servants and in some cases, teachers are owed many months of salary areas.

Problems of Staffing - There are problem on the quality and quantity of staff recruited for the education of our citizens. The reason is from poor staff recruitment and selection process. Politicians and God fatherism has taken the upper hand. Some staff rarely stay in the remote areas where the management wants their services (Omebe C., 2014).

Institutional Contexts: Pressures for Change

Global markets mean that universities need increasingly to compete globally with other knowledge providers for highly qualified staff. Whereas, in the past, relatively homogeneous conditions of employment and linear career structures offered stability and predictability, contemporary universities are now part of “a very complex knowledge producing game” (Gibbons et al., 1994, p. 65), which obliges them to seek new and different skills in a volatile environment (Wood, 2005). Universities are also faced with conflicting pressures. For instance, even allowing for international variance, they face encouragement to both collaborate and compete with each other and this has led to operational as well as disciplinary complexities (Barnett 2003, p. 184-185). These complexities relate not only to structures and systems, but also to the organization and development of staff, both in terms of workforce planning and the local management of individuals. At the same time, approaches to work and working life are changing. Staff in their 20s and 30s are said to value access to information, opportunities for networking, and a balanced lifestyle as much as the traditional milestones and status offered by a professional career. Additionally, a proportion of younger staff do not necessarily anticipate a career for life, and look to acquire experience that will be distinctive, equipping them for a future that is more uncertain than it was for their predecessors

Academic staff

This evolving environment is impacting on higher education institutions around the world, although there are substantial geographical and intra-sectorial differences in the pace of change, the precise nature of the implications for staff, and the reactions of staff and other stakeholders. What some may see as

threats, others may perceive as liberating or legitimising developments. Much has been written on the intensification of academic work (Harman, 2003; McInnis, 1999), pressures to adapt roles and practices, resistance to such forces (Shattock, 2000), and a tendency to favour change strategies of accumulation and accretion (Coaldrake and Stedman, 1999). Perhaps not surprisingly, given the foregoing points, the literature also reports growing concerns about workloads, stress, issues of work-life balance, and widespread opposition to a perceived increase in unwanted bureaucracy.

Training and Development the role of administration

Training and development are the heart of the efforts to sustainably improve the personnel competency and organizational performance (Mondy, 2018:210). Training provides the participants the knowledge and skills required for their current tasks. Development involves educating the personnel beyond the need for the current tasks and is focused for long term goals. Employees who always be in step with the changes and growth of the organization are to be prepared in the development process. The universities may have highly qualified professionals in different subject areas, but have pedagogical difficulties. They must therefore identify an adapted approach for the new challenges they are facing today.

Relevance of Human Resources Management (HRM) in Administration:

An educational institution is unable to build a good team of professionals without good Human Resources. The key functions of the Human Resources Management (HRM) are in the following:

- (i) **Recruitment and Training:** This is one of the major responsibilities of the human resource management team. The HR managers come up with plans and strategies for hiring the right kind of people. They design the criteria which is best suited for a specific job description. Their other tasks related to recruitment include formulating the obligations of an employee and the scope of tasks assigned to him or her. Based on these two factors, the contract of an employee with the company is prepared. When needed, they also provide training to the employees according to the requirements of the organization. Thus, the staff members get the opportunity to sharpen their existing skills or develop specialized skills which in turn, will help them to take up some new roles.
- (ii) **Performance Appraisals:** HRM encourages the people working in an organization, to work according to their potential and gives them suggestions that can help them to bring about improvement in it. The team communicates with the staff individually from time to time and provides all the necessary information regarding their performances and also defines their respective roles. This is beneficial as it enables them to form an outline of their anticipated goals in much clearer terms and thereby, helps them execute the goals with best possible efforts. Performance appraisals, when taken on a regular basis, motivate the employees.
- (iii) **Maintaining Work Atmosphere:** This is a vital aspect of HRM because the performance of an individual in an organization is largely driven by the work atmosphere or work culture that prevails at

the workplace. A good working condition is one of the benefits that the employees can expect from an efficient human resource team. A safe, clean and healthy environment can bring out the best in an employee. A friendly atmosphere gives the staff members' job satisfaction as well.

(iv) **Managing Disputes:** Conflicts are almost inevitable in an organization. In a School there are several issues on which disputes may arise between the employees and the employers. In such a scenario, it is the human resource department which acts as a consultant and mediator to sort out those issues in an effective manner. They first hear the grievances of the employees. Then they come up with suitable solutions to sort them out. In other words, they take timely action and prevent things from going out of hands.

(v) **Developing Public Relations:** The responsibility of establishing good public relations lies with the HRM to a great extent. They organize business meetings, seminars and various official gatherings on behalf of the school in order to build up relationships with other sectors of the economy. Any organization, without a proper setup for HRM is bound to suffer from serious problems while managing its regular activities. For this reason, today, companies must put a lot of effort and energy into setting up a strong and effective HRM (Usman, Yunusa Dangara, 2016).

Conclusion:

Accessibility of education resources has always been regarded as an essential and integral part of school administration and basically geared towards the improvement of all other factors in teaching and learning process thus ensuring qualitative service delivery by the school to the society. The success of the schools depends among others on effective school administration with good leadership, proper time management in the school system, allocation of ample financial resources to schools, regular training and re-training of human resources in the school, perfect interrelationship with the community and ingenious utilization of the available resources in the school system. A picture emerges, therefore, of a diverse and mobile workforce, for whom the content of roles is changing, sometimes by default, and sometimes via policy interventions by governments or institutions, such as the modification of terms and conditions. On this note, it is clear that development of a country is based on the general quality of life and quality labor or quality of work life of the country, while quality of work life of the population is a function of Human Resource Development of the total population (McMichael, 2011). The shift in the paradigm of economic- based measurement of development to human- development based- measurement is informed by the reasoning that economic progression of any country is dependent on the quality of skills and health of the population. Human resource development in higher education institutions are the most important factors for improving employee work performance, as well as increasing daily duties in serving the public and also as a strategic investment in the world of work and organizations. administration institutions, which are largely responsible for the bureaucracy in providing services to

the community, must be supported by professional and competent Human Resources (HR) staff. Higher education institutions are required to have innovations in the bureaucracy to develop various policies and support administrative functions.

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